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Trauma and Memory: War and Refugees

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Abstract:

Trauma studies hold a cardinal position in evincing the physiological and psychological impact of the victims who travel along with the memories of suffering throughout their lives. Such people are marginalized and undergo a series of oppression in their lives and find it extremely difficult to cope. Victims who strive for peace and positive change attempt to divert their minds from the life of monotony to excitement. Trauma stick deep rooted into the minds of the victims and it takes a long years to come out of their emotional dependency. There are many refugees who had undergone multiple oppression and found it extremely demanding to make the opponents understand their life of repression. Most countries face wars every day in different corner of the world and experience internal and external conflicts of wars, directly or indirectly. Humankind should learn compassion and respect humanity to comprehend and save the victims from any form of suffering. This present paper traverse about how diverse wars pave way to trauma and the distressing memories that eventually haunt and provide nightmares to lead a life of leisure.

Keywords: Brutality, Haunting war memories, Loss of identity, Marginalisation, Memory, Oppression, Partition, Trauma, War.

War is never fought only for freedom and in most of the occasion it happens just to satisfy the personal egoistic clash of different nations. In the eighteenth century, wars were represented as a noble pursuit and a way for the individuals to achieve honor and glory in their lives to be an invincible part of serving the nation. In those times, violence was magnified and children perished more than the soldiers in the callous wars. Later on, literature emerged as a powerful tool for understanding and representing the complexities and the dark world of war. World War I had a significant role in inspiring the writers of the twentieth century as they were filled with indignation at the injustice of the prevailing situation of the century.

Waging a war against any nation is considered a noble thought. Moreover, it has definitely taken many years for normal people to perceive the dark side of war that overshadowed the congenial life of the victims. The eighteenth century British poets who preferred to write on the theme of war were fondly addressed as “war poets”. The significant war poets Wilfred Owen, Siegfried Sassoon, Rupert Brooke, Robert Graves and Isaac Rosenberg laid a great platform to showcase the duties of soldiers and painful situation of soldiers in the arena of war.

In the poem “Soldier”, Rupert Brooke proclaimed his patriotic fervent towards his country, England and also propagated on the need of war and to leave the world as a martyr. In the poem “Anthem for Doomed Youth” despite being a World War I combatant, Wilfred Owen exposes the harsh realities of war instead of glorifying it. The whole poem unveils the fact that the death of the soldiers was the price of wars.

In the short story “Foreigner” by Christopher Burns, the author intricately weaves the trauma of the mother of a dead soldier where she believed that wars are absolutely unnecessary for any nation as that results in the casualties of innocent soldiers. This particular short story sheds light on the absurdity of wars as the soldier who kills the opponent soldier is oblivious of name, religion or ambition of the dead person. In the short story, Debbie’s ex-husband, a veteran

soldier supports the prospective of war “It’s the past that makes us what we are” and Debbie, the mother of Alex whom she lost in war gets infuriated by the thoughts of war and nation. Debbie questions: “How does it feel knowing that your boy will never return home? How does it feel to know that somebody else’s boy will never return home because of you?”

In India, patriotic poets like Mahakavi Bharathiar, and Rabindranath Tagore ignited the young minds on the importance of fighting for freedom from British people. The influential poem “Where the Mind is without Fear” taken from Tagore’s inspiring collection “Gitanjali” boldly asserts the need of a nation where juvenile and liberated minds to live without a fear and are being phenomenally resilient. Likewise, knowledge has to be accessible to everyone as the world not merely divided by artificial boundaries for the sake of the individuals, “Where the world has not been broken up into fragments.”

By narrow domestic walls.” Sarojini Naidu’s patriotic poem, “The Gift of India” manifests the plight of the Indian soldiers who bravely fought alongside the British in World War I. War indicates the altruistic behaviour and sacrifice of the Indian soldiers and reminds the world about the loss of innocent lives of the valiant soldiers.

When the terror and tumult of hate shall cease
And life be refashioned on anvils of peace,
And your love shall offer memorial thanks
To the comrades who fought in your dauntless ranks,
And you honour the deeds of the deathless ones
Remember the blood of thy martyred sons! (Naidu)

George Bernard Shaw’s *Arms and the Man* examines the romantic views of war where the warfront has never been to showcase the heroism of the soldiers. Doris Lessing in “Laboratories of Social Change”, examines wars which have ended only in bloodshed and people who are

oblivious of rules of tyranny alone neglect democratic government. The war victims often undergo much trauma in their lives and also face anguish in every situation of life. In Michael Ondaatje's *The English Patient*, through the eponymous character, English patient, the writer exemplifies the trauma and suffering in war, the personal losses, and identity crisis. Those victims are invariably affected by war and its impact, and the consequences of war had resulted in bloodshed.

The Diary of a Young Girl by Anne Frank presents a vivid representation of the experiences of Anne Frank in her gifted diary in which she recorded her thoughts and emotions "Because paper has more patience than people." (Frank). Through her diary, the readers perceived the problems and suffering of the Jews who were treated just like animals and not as humans. They were not treated equally and never allowed to live their lives peacefully. At the time of World War II, Germany invaded Netherlands, and Anne Frank recorded her two years of confinement between the years 1942-44. This diary plays a crucial role as she has recorded everyday events along with fear of life and hope for freedom while staying in the "Secret Annex". She fondly addressed her diary as "Kitty", and she disclosed her trauma and pain only to the confidant, diary. Unfortunately, the world lost the valiant girl who recorded all the events from her thirteenth birthday. While she was alive, her family faced a lot of challenging situations where it was impossible to cough, sneeze, use bathroom frequently, short supply of provisions for significant number of people, and the dresses turned too small to fit them in. The whole day, they sat without making any noise and not talking to each other. Amidst the struggles, the family was arrested and confined in the concentration camps where women were forced to stand naked to undergo much physical abuse. If ever Anne Frank had failed to record the events of concentration camp and in confinement, then the world would have miserably failed to perceive the blood history behind the curtain of war. If Anne Frank had survived, she would

have been the shining star of resilience and determination “I wish to go on living even after my death.” (Frank).

Ernest Hemingway’s *Farewell to Arms* poignantly records the adverse effects of war on psyche at the time of First World War. Frederic Henry, an American hero of the novel enrolled himself in the Italian army was indeed fighting against the combined armies of Austria and Germany. This writer was audacious to present the realistic and raw version of war that it leads only to destruction and a brutal experience.

It is generally said that Hemingway is a novelist of ‘lost generation’. The ‘lost generation’ stands for the 1920s when people had not only been wounded physically by war and violence but also injured psychologically and spiritually because of a feeling of dread and fear, uncertainty and confusion. The First World War had spelt total disaster in the form of a collapse of all established and traditional values. (Singh)

Kurt Vonnegut’s *Slaughterhouse-Five* presents a tapestry of interwoven events which focus on the physical wounds and psychological trauma of the war victims who suffer awful loss of their beloved people. The incident eventually disturb the lives of the individuals/ innocent victims and took decision to live the rest of their lives bereft of hope. Ultimate destruction of the land and people bereft of any positive outcome or a morality to live their life indicate the futility of any world war. The novel propagates the irrationality of governments, which swindle the innocent lives of people and the future of the nation. The writer was being determined to present true colour of war, which explores the trauma and suffering of individuals.

Rebecca West’s *The Return of the Soldier* is a manifestation of the conflict of war, which resulted in the psychological trauma of Captain Chris Barley, who recently returned from the

trenches of I World War. Protagonist suffered exhaustively from shell shock and amnesia, and reveals the disparity between the relationships in the aftermath of the war.

The focal point of the novel, *Hiroshima* edges on the events of the atomic bomb explosion, which was dropped on the Japanese city on the *August 6*, 1945. This novel documents the trauma of war through the personal stories of six survivors of the bomb attack. This novel never ceased to grab the attention of the readers by showcasing the psychological and physical effects of war on the victims of the locality who struggled hard to rebuild their lives amidst the terrible loss of lives and wealth “When he had penetrated the bushes, he saw there were about twenty men, and they were all in exactly the same nightmarish state: their faces were wholly burned, their eyesockets were hollow, the fluid from their melted eyes...” (Hersey, 68). This novel is the first of its kind to record the events before and after the war through the six survivors. Bombing has approximately killed 2 lakh people, and the novel explores in detail regarding the incidents from the detonation and the tragic effects of bombing on the lives of innocent people who struggle each day to meet their ends meet. As a war correspondent, the writer encapsulates the readers with his first-hand information from the warfront. The victims faced much of health ailments due to radiation effect, which resulted in maladies, unknown and unnamed diseases, Down syndrome and diagnosed with a spot hemorrhages.

The rays had a devastating effect on the body cells and after a few days, the patients developed the symptoms of diarrhea, malaise and fever. In the second stage, the foremost symptom was hair fall, diarrhea and fever. After a month, the patients are diagnosed with the blood disorders and the bleeding gums. Even the count of the white blood cells dropped and then identified was anemia. The doctors faced a huge downfall when they had insufficient equipment and instruments to treat the survivors. (Karunya 62)

Khushwant Singh's *Train to Pakistan* exposes the traumatic incidents of the partition between India and Pakistan. This story was set in a fictional village, Manoj Majra, and the novel focuses on the forced migration of millions of refugees, Hindu population from Pakistan and Muslims from India. Once upon a time, the village with Hindus, Muslims and Sikhs lived in harmony before the partition and disruption arose soon after the partition of India. The Trauma is often associated with loss, grief and deaths, innumerable rapes and riots. Victims undergo a lot of mental agonies as the destiny made them witness a lot of bloodshed and trains of cruelly massacred dead bodies. Villagers were oblivious of "By the summer of 1947, when the creation of the new state of Pakistan was formally announced, ten million people- Muslims and Hindus and Sikhs- were in fight. By the time the monsoon broke, almost a million of them were dead, and all of northern India was in arms, in terror, or in hiding." (Singh 2). Refugees were terrified at the ghost trains which carried millions of dead Sikhs, and the village of peace and harmony turned to be the abode of social unrest where injustice and brutal activities were witnessed.

Bapsi Sidwa's *Ice Candy Man* represents a poignant narrative of the partition of India through the eyes of eight year old Parsi girl, Lenny. Lenny was a crippled daughter of a wealthy Parsee family who became crippled by polio. Bapsi Sidwa highlighted the plight of women who endured all sorts of humiliation and patriarchal dominance. Cruelty or harsh reality of partition is that everyone should be away from home and their homeland; it divides people in the name of religion and community. Prior to Independence, India had British as an enemy and after partition, Pakistan emerged as an enemy nation of partitioned India. One day, the nurse-maid of Lenny, Ayah (Shanta) was admired for her beauty irrespective of any religion and later on, due to religious intolerance among men, she was mercilessly abducted, gang raped and forced into prostitution by a mob of her admirers. "it is sudden. One day everybody is themselves- and the next day they are Hindu, Muslim, Sikh, Christian. People shrink,

dwindling into symbols. Ayah is no longer my all-compassing Ayah, she is also a token. A Hindu...” (Cracking India, p. 101)

Similar to the incidents in the above mentioned novels, Chaman Nahal’s *Azadi* informs the reading audience of the trauma of war and the haunting memories which was being endured by victims for an extended period of time. The novel propagates the physical and emotional impact of war and the fragmented identities of the nation post partition. Owing to war, economy of a nation descends to a greater extent, and nations turned to be dependent on the other nations for the basic support. If humanity truly exists, then people will stand together in unison in thought and action, and never divided by their religion, race or caste. Wars and the impact of war are not just for the current situation, but also for the future. It has an inevitable role to play in the lives of millions of victims, and the consequences of war are the recurring terrific memories in those lives. Furthermore, wars are indeed a collective memory as it warrant the lives of different populace put in a single frame.

Salman Rushdie’s *Midnight Children* renders the theme of the birth of two nations, India and Pakistan through the birth of Saleem Sinai and his twin, Shiva being born at midnight. This partition was never a smooth sail, somewhat, a political turmoil or unrest. Indeed, the novel highlights major historical events of India like partition, Indian independence, Indo-China war, Indo- Bangladesh war and Indira Gandhi’s Emergency.

Alan Gratz’s *Refugee* encompasses the stories of three children who were forced to flee their sweet homes and the native due to unexpected political upheaval. A real identity of three children—Josef, a 12 year- old Jewish boy fleeing Germany during II World War; a Cuban girl of eleven years old gave her best to cross the ocean to Miami in 1994; Mahmoud, a Syrian boy of thirteen years old was being caught in the hurricane of civil war. This book records the terrific tale of three children along with family members, to reach their planned destination in order to escape from the clutches of warfront. This novel is indeed the book of coming of age

of three protagonists. Despite being enjoying the joy of childhood, those three children are forced to take up the responsibility of adults. A journey they have undertaken to reach their planned destination was challenging and complicated. They faced many hurdles, and every moment was uncertain of their life and journey. They become knowledgeable about life from being innocent. Living amidst diverse tribulation and violence, those survivors had a ray of hope of their future.

The Little Liar by Mitch Albom captivated the readers with the first-hand information regarding the holocaust and the terrific experiences of the Jews under the regime of Hitler. This story set during the Holocaust in Salonika, and a young Jewish boy, Nico Krispis, unknown for his unwavering honest was been manipulated by a Nazi officer, who made the young boy in reassuring the Jewish residents that they are being sent to “new homes” in a train when they were actually being transported to concentration camps. Therefore, Nico’s older brother, Sebastian is enraged at the behavior and attitude of Nico. Owing to war and the holocaust, these children had to lose their innocence of infancy or the childhood. Nico realized the bitter truth that the train was indeed heading towards Auschwitz, a death camp for the Jews.

The world has never been created to be divided by thoughts, religion, ideology, doctrine, caste, creed and language. Humankind have to be united in their thought and action and make the world an abode of peace and harmony. Literature is a powerful medium to represent the multitude of incidents those happen around the world. The diverse genres of literature explore diverse traumatic events which are imprinted on the minds of the victims and destined to carry the memories till their last breath. The memories are truly haunting, and psychological scars are irreplaceable and inflict agony even after long years. Mankind should end the concept of war and make attempts to solve any problems and issues through mutual respect and understanding. Our life will be a blessing where the world is without war and arrogance and full of joy and prosperity.

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